

Automated Construction Progress Tracking Systems: An Industry Perspective to Implementation Drivers and Barriers

Purpose – This paper examines the current state of Automated Construction Progress Tracking Systems (ACPTS) and clarifies the factors influencing their limited adoption in the construction industry. It outlines the capabilities of existing ACPTS, identifies key benefits and challenges, and explores how U.S. construction professionals perceive these systems across different project contexts. The paper expands construction technology adoption research by incorporating financial, cultural, technical, and personal dimensions often overlooked in previous studies.

Design/methodology/approach – A mixed-methods approach was used, combining a screening survey with interviews involving U.S. construction professionals experienced in progress monitoring and digital workflows. Data was analyzed and grouped into four themes—Financial, Cultural, Technical, and Personal considerations—to capture diverse drivers and barriers affecting ACPTS adoption.

Findings – The study provides empirical insights into the perceived advantages and limitations of ACPTS. While ACPTS offers improved accuracy, faster progress assessment, reduced disputes, and enhanced decision-making, adoption remains hindered by high initial cost, cultural resistance to change, technical integration challenges, and differing individual perceptions of value. These factors collectively shape organizational readiness and influence decisions regarding implementation.

Practical implications – The study offers insights to help organizations assess ACPTS readiness, anticipate adoption challenges, and make more informed implementation decisions.

Originality/value – This paper contributes industry-grounded evidence on multi-dimensional factors shaping ACPTS adoption and provides a framework for evaluating organizational readiness for automated progress tracking technologies.

Keywords: Automation, Construction Progress Tracking, Technology Drivers and Barriers, Automated Progress Tracking, Construction Projects, ACPTS adoption.

Introduction

Construction projects are inherently complex and dynamic, with unforeseen events and conditions frequently occurring, leading to changes in duration and costs (Rebolj et al., 2008). The unpredictable nature of construction projects emphasizes the need for accurate and prompt assessments of the current as-built progress status (Alizadehsalehi et al., 2019b). However, traditional progress tracking methods are time-intensive, expensive, and can be associated with potential errors, inconsistencies, and uncertainties—often contingent on the proficiency of inspectors (Golparvar-Fard et al., 2011). Hence, a need exists for a more efficient and productive approach to processing, reading, visualizing, and effectively storing project progress information.

Despite efforts to simplify project monitoring by using advanced computer technologies and the fact that construction professionals are keen to automate project progress control (Zhang et al., 2013), the construction industry lags in adopting automated innovations compared to other industries (Davila Delgado et al., 2019). Barriers such as lack of skilled workers, high implementation and maintenance costs, and insufficient knowledge about the advantages of ACPTS are some of the factors that hinder its widespread adoption (Alizadehsalehi et al., 2019a).

While previous studies have evaluated the technical aspects of ACPTS technologies, including implementation, benefits, and drawbacks (Abreu et al., 2023; Amirthavarshan et al., 2023; X. Chen et al., 2022; Ekanayake et al., 2021; Kopsida, 2015; Omar et al., 2018; Sami Ur Rehman, 2022), there remains a significant gap in understanding how industry professionals perceive ACPTS. This study aims to bridge this research gap by providing real-world experiences from construction experts and general contractors.

The objective of this study is to collect industry perspectives on the benefits and barriers to using ACPTS for construction projects. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following research questions:

- What are the key drivers and barriers to the implementation of ACPTS in General Contractor (GC) companies in the USA?
- How do these drivers and barriers contribute to differences in attitudes toward the implementation of ACPTS in construction management?

To achieve the objectives of this study and to answer the research questions, a mixed-method research approach was employed to deeply explore general contractor's attitudes towards this technology. This methodology encompassed the distribution of screening surveys and a series of interviews with construction professionals operating in the USA. This approach allows the study to highlight industry professionals' perspectives, providing valuable insights for potential adopters of ACPTS to make an informed decision before technology implementation in their projects. Additionally, the findings lay the groundwork for future research to develop a roadmap for ACPTS implementation and decision-making processes.

Literature Review

A comprehensive literature review was conducted to provide background and insights into ACPTS, forming the foundation of this research. The review followed a transparent and structured

methodology, with inclusion criteria based on relevance to ACPTS in the areas of data acquisition (DAQ), data analysis, and visualization within the construction industry, and Exclusion criteria included non-English articles, opinion pieces without empirical data, and studies focusing on unrelated aspects of construction technology. Priority was given to peer-reviewed and reputable sources that offered meaningful insight into the implications of ACPTS. The literature was then analyzed to identify common themes, including:

1. Benefits and challenges of ACPTS as technology and its related technologies in construction and the potential to automate and semi-automate CPT (Construction progress tracking), reporting, and analyzing data.
2. Implementation strategies to highlight how this system is integrated into existing workflows.
3. Efficiency and performance outcomes focus on the project’s cost, schedule, and performance control.

The literature review focused on sources published between 2010 and 2024, encompassing academic journals, Conference papers, and relevant books. The scope was specifically narrowed to studies discussing technological means and methods, and advancements in ACPTS. Furthermore, a structured search strategy was implemented using databases such as Emerald, ScienceDirect, ASCE, and Google Scholar. Keywords used in the search included “Automated construction tracking”, “Construction management technology”, “Progress monitoring in construction”, “Advantages and barriers of technology in construction” and” Digital twin in construction”, “Progress tracking”. Searches were refined by using filters like 'date range', 'English language', and 'citation count' to ensure the relevance and quality of sources.

Figure 1 represents the hierarchy diagram for the literature review, illustrating how the various sections and subsections relate to one another.

Figure 1: Data Acquisition Technologies

Technologies employed in DAQ can be categorized into four distinct groups including enhanced IT, Geospatial technologies, Imaging techniques, and Augmented Reality applications (Omar et al., 2016). Each category encompasses a variety of methods and strategies designed to achieve specific goals, presenting a unique blend of benefits and challenges. Among these technologies, radio frequency identification (RFID), Barcodes and QR codes, GIS (Geographic information system), GPS (Global Positioning System), GNSS (Global navigation satellite system), laser scanning, photogrammetry, and videogrammetry, and range images are investigated for their applicability in ACPTS (Omar et al., 2016). Table 1 illustrates the advantages and disadvantages of these DAQ technologies.

TABLE 1: Advantages and disadvantages of DAQ technologies (M. Kopsida et al., 2015; Moselhi et al., 2020; Najibifar et al., 2025; Omar et al., 2016; Pal et al., 2023; Rehman et al., 2022)

		Advantages	Disadvantages
Geospatial Tools	Barcoding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capable of DAQ and information retrieval Versatility for different tasks High capacity of data content & type Data accuracy and integrity Ease of production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manual error modification Dependent online-of-sight Physical wear and tears Limited to static data Scalability concerns
	RFID	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capable of DAQ and information retrieval Automated identification Integration with BIM-based inspection software Easy access to information with smartphones or tablets Substantial reading range No direct line-of-sight needed Durability in different environments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manual error modification High initial cost Limited operation lifespan Battery replacement Interferences from metals Long installation and maintenance time (>1 hour) Semi-automated
	GIS and GPS, GNSS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automatic error modification Capable of DAQ, information retrieval, progress monitoring, and output visualization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less effective in congested environments GPS accuracy degradation and accuracy issues Expensive to attach GPS receiver to all the objects The data includes only object positions and times, excluding identity or activity details.
Imaging technology	Photo-grammetry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Most cost-effective Easiest to carry (portability) Generating 3D models or point clouds of construction sites from digital photos Efficient Data Gathering 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Long processing time Vulnerability due to Light Variations Monitoring limitations: effective for components closest to the camera Need for Manual Oversight
	Video-grammetry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capable of DAQ, information retrieval, progress monitoring, and output visualization More cost effective than laser scanning Moderate accuracy compared to laser scanning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Long processing time Short-range limitations Challenges in identifying consecutive activities accurately Not effective in capturing the intricacies of construction activities effectively
	Laser Scanning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Long- range distance Most accurate point clouds Fastest processing time real time segmentation in new cameras integration with 4D tracking capable of fully automated document management and automated data analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Most expensive Technology requires a clear line of sight Limited application in congested environment Object differentiation issues in a point cloud Time-consuming segmentation process for object detection

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • automated capability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires expert interpretation for data analysis • Reduced flexibility compared to photogrammetry when changes or updates are needed
Range images		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capable of DAQ, information retrieval, real time progress monitoring, and output visualization • Cost effective approach for 3D shape of objects' digitalization • Accurate data capture for tracking objects • Not dependent on the backlighting • Comprehensive visual data with a wide FOV • Versatility for short-range application • Cheaper than laser scanning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Least accurate point clouds • Short-range limitations • More expensive than photogrammetry • Not suitable for long-range scanning in large construction sites

Sensor Mounting Techniques

Imaging technologies utilize diverse sensor mounting techniques for generating image frames, videos, and point clouds. Deployment options for these sensors in data acquisition (DAQ) range from fixed devices and handheld units to site cameras, robotic systems on unmanned ground vehicles (UGVs), unmanned aircraft vehicles (UAVs), or a combination of these systems (Reja et al., 2022). Table 2 outlines sensor mounting methods, including their benefits and limitations.

TABLE 2: Advantages and disadvantages of sensor mounting techniques (Sami Ur Rehman et al., 2022a; Barbarosoglu, 2021; Hamledari et al., 2021; Li et al., 2021; Pecoraro et al., 2017; Tutta et al., 2016; Golparvar-Fard et al., 2011)

Techniques	Advantages	Disadvantages
Handheld devices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficiency: The system saves project management staff's time by automating DAQ and analysis • Adaptability: Handheld devices offer flexibility in DAQ, adapting to varying site conditions • flexibility in DAQ by adapting to varying site conditions and types of data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited Coverage: Handheld devices have restricted reach, leading to incomplete data collection. • Reliance on Manual Labor: Despite automation, Manual data collection can introduce errors and inefficiencies. • Complexity: Implementing advanced tech may add complexity and require specialized expertise.
Fixed on mounts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quadruped robots, equipped with cameras or laser scans, autonomously explore construction sites, collecting progress data using AI. • Connects to cloud-based systems, providing real-time updates on site progress 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May not provide complete site coverage, resulting in fragmented point clouds
Unmanned aircraft vehicles (UAVs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UAV-enabled techniques are more efficient with better coverage. • Compatible with 4D for indoor inspection • They can navigate building interiors that are inaccessible to ground vehicles, capture high-resolution images and videos, and perform remote laser scanning. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High initial costs • Short battery life and associated flight time • Intricate hardware and software interfaces • Accidents can occur due to misunderstandings regarding drone precision and tolerance. • Tough regulations can increase UAV technology adoption costs in construction (Li et al., 2021; Pecoraro et al., 2017)

Choosing a sensor mounting method involves considering eight critical elements: legal permissions, hardware cost, operational scope, intended application, operator training,

navigational capabilities, maneuvering speed, and system accessibility (Najibifar et al., 2025; Reja et al., 2022).

Data Retrieval and Progress Analysis

In the construction industry, the information gathered from job sites provides project management teams with insights into the actual progress of the project, such as physical advancements, hours worked, materials used, and equipment employed. (Hegazy, 2013). The collected data from the activities, whether through point cloud interpretations, images, videos, and/or datasets, are acquired as a as-built representation. This is then analyzed by comparing it with the as-planned model or schedule to determine the progression of different construction activities (J. Chen et al., 2019), helping the project team to determine whether the project is behind, on track, or ahead of its planned pace, and allows for strategizing potential modifications if necessary (Kopsida, 2015). As previously mentioned, the types of data that can be collected from construction projects vary based on the data acquisition methods employed. The section below delves into the data retrieval and progress analysis systems.

Photogrammetry

To assess construction progress in a precise and systematic manner, a comprehensive process centered on the analysis of the collated point cloud data, images, or videos is typically employed. This data is then superimposed on the project’s BIM model, a process known as registration. This registration phase demands post-processing of the acquired data to eliminate noise and extract useful information (Kopsida, 2015). Following this, the volume of the actual built structure is gauged and contrasted with the projected construction volume (Abreu et al., 2023). BIM's inclusion of various objects, building spaces, and their interrelationships provides efficient as-planned models for comparing as-built data to estimate progress (Sami Ur Rehman et al., 2022b). Commonly, a 4D model, which integrates the project’s schedule, acts as the as-planned representation. The as-built versions are subsequently overlaid on this 4D model to enable a direct comparison between the intended and actual models (Kopsida, 2015).

Various kinds of as-built models exist, such as models based on control points, voxel representations, mesh frameworks, surface models, and industry foundation classes (IFC)-Based structures (Sami Ur Rehman, 2022). Table 3 highlights the functionality of each as-built model technique.

TABLE 3: Computational Requirements based on the type of as-built model (Reja et al., 2022; Sami Ur Rehman et al., 2022a)

As-Built Model Type	Progress Display		Progress Measurement	
	Computational Requirements for Modeling	Quality of Output	Computational Requirements for Quantitative Analysis	Accuracy of Quantities
IFC Model	Very high	Very high	Very Low	Very High
Surface Model	High	High	Low	High

Mesh Model	Low	Medium	High	Medium
Voxel Model	Low	Medium	High	Low
Point Cloud	Very Low	Low	Very High	Very Low

Elements recognition

Elements recognition leverages pre-coded domain knowledge to identify construction elements from control points, with techniques to categorize elements like walls, panels, and ducts (Wang et al., 2021). These approaches utilize object-oriented models to extract valuable progress data, which can be enhanced through machine learning automation. Machine learning models efficiently analyze extensive data or images from construction sites by uncovering hidden patterns and insights. Integrated into progress monitoring tools, they enhance automated data assessment and progress-tracking efficiency (Pan et al., 2021). For example, (Deng et al., 2020) employed the improved edge detection algorithm that detects the boundaries of completed tiles in given images to be compared with the BIM. Greeshma and Edayadiyil (2022) developed an automated system utilizing image processing and machine learning for masonry wall progress-tracking.

Digital Twin

The concept of a digital twin (DT) offers the prospect of seamlessly merging the physical realm with the digital domain (Amirthavarshan et al., 2023). Automated data acquisition from construction sites and supply chains, combined with AI integration, establishes a construction paradigm using digital twin information systems. This framework introduces four fundamental information and control concepts for digital twin construction (DTC), delineating the dimensions of the conceptual space (Sacks et al., 2020). However, the novelty of DT and the lack of case studies poses challenges in understanding its value and implementation hurdles (Pal et al., 2024; redacted, 2025a; Simchenko et al., 2019; Singh et al., 2021).

Research on construction asset cyber-physical systems shows the use of RFID tags, scanners, and various sensors (e.g., location, load, displacement), forming an interconnected sensor network. This network enables continuous communication between on-site sensors and a virtual model, providing real-time information for the planned model (Morris, 2003). The Published research highlights data-BIM misalignment, suggesting scan-to-BIM for detailed site imagery. However, this approach faces storage, filtering, and alignment challenges due to the volume of visual data. Integrating sensors with varying capabilities, frequencies, and locations poses key challenges in DT, notably regarding spatiotemporal resolutions (Boje et al., 2020).

Vision-based techniques and DT integration. This type of model requires the localization of components, which can be achieved by integrating BIM and an initial map of the construction site (Asadi et al., 2019; redacted, 2025b). The automated vision-based technique faces challenges, particularly in the completeness of 3D reconstruction, significantly impacting the automatic registration method. In complex construction projects, the presence of various temporary facilities introduces significant noise. While studies have addressed this issue, a comprehensive solution for dynamic construction scenarios is yet to be realized (Pal et al., 2023).

Automatic project schedule update. Regular schedule updates are crucial for project management. However, the availability of updated 4D BIM at construction sites is limited (Pal et al., 2023). Automating project schedule updates involves linking reality models with construction schedules, a process facilitated by 3D BIM or pre-surveyed control points. One-step point-cloud segmentation, as identified by Park et al. (2022), is utilized to identify building components, followed by image segmentation to segment reality capture images based on material appearances. Despite these vision-based advancements, manual progress input persists.

Data Visualization

Output visualization involves displaying relevant data or outcomes derived from information gathering or progress assessment (Sami Ur Rehman, 2022). Effective on-site data collection and prompt data analysis are essential, along with proficient visualization of progress inspection outcomes, often illustrated through extended reality (XR). XR, particularly AR, has emerged as a practical method for visualizing construction project advancements, enabling near-real-time comparison of 3D as-planned and as-built project status (Pal et al., 2023). Halder et al. (2022) introduced a real-time approach using a quadruped robot for walk-throughs and AR for as-planned and as-built verification. Mixed reality (MR) environments allow physical and virtual objects to coexist and interact in real-time, offering unique opportunities for real-time progress detection, visualization, and decision-making (Omar & Nehdi, 2016).

Ma (2019) introduced a 4D AR system using the as-designed AR model to compare with the as-built site, offering a proactive solution for data visualization. This system showcased an automated AR registration method with relative coordinates and a fixed camera, but in the lab setting and utilizing a straightforward building mock, to present a dynamic animation of the construction process.

In terms of advantages, integrating MR in construction lies in its ability to offer a visual assessment of physical construction progress on the worksite. However, a limitation is observed in its intricate processing for registration and the absence of real-time visualization capability (Sami Ur Rehman, 2022). Another challenge is ensuring precise synchronization between computer-generated graphics and real-world information. This challenge largely hinges on correctly determining the user's viewpoint and location (M. Kopsida et al., 2015). Various AR-centric inspection methods use bulky equipment on tripods for precision but face mobility limitations (Côté et al., 2013).

The other method that can be employed to facilitate the decision-making process based on the progress-tracking data is earned value management (EVM). Automating the computation of EVM metrics can offer essential data for project oversight, pinpointing possible setbacks. Turkan et al. (2013) proposed a fully automated system with terrestrial laser scanning to periodically gather 3D point clouds, capturing time-lapsed, as-built data. When aligned with a 4D model detailing the planned project progress, it facilitates automatic EVM generation. However, automated EVM analysis and reporting have been rarely explored in the existing literature (Sami Ur Rehman, 2022).

Methodology

To fulfill the objectives of this study, a mixed-method research methodology was employed, aiming to gain in-depth insight into the attitudes of general contractors towards ACPTS. The rationale behind choosing this approach lies in the objective of gathering detailed, comprehensive insights from industry experts regarding this novel system. Engaging with these professionals directly through mixed-method techniques provides an opportunity to explore their perspectives, experiences, and viewpoints in depth. These insights are vital in assessing the barriers and drivers in the use of ACPTS in the construction industry. The methodology included conducting a literature review, creating, and distributing a screening survey, and conducting a series of interviews with qualified construction professionals. Although the literature review incorporated research from all the scholars and resources, the study concentrated on obtaining perspectives from GCs and professionals in the USA. This distinction enables the research to offer industry insights that are contextually relevant while considering a wide array of technical assessments and discoveries, from the existing body of literature.

Survey Development and Distribution

A cross-sectional survey design was used to identify potential candidates for subsequent interviews. The screening survey was employed to filter potential and interested candidates for the qualitative phase (interviews). Given that ACPTS is still in the initial stages of adoption within the construction industry, the initial pool of four hundred potential candidates was too large to engage directly in qualitative interviews. The screening survey helped reduce this pool to a manageable number while maintaining diversity in perspectives.

The survey was distributed via email to a compiled list of four hundred potential respondents derived from extensive research on various general contractor companies, service providers, and professionals across different sectors of construction. The survey instrument was crafted to gather insights from construction industry professionals regarding their current use of ACPTS and their familiarity with various techniques associated with ACPTS. The questionnaire predominantly featured closed-ended questions, providing respondents with predetermined answer choices. This survey structure, refined through expert input and pilot testing with a sample of general contractors, is designed to capture a wide range of insights, from practical challenges to strategic benefits, shaping a nuanced understanding of ACPTS in the construction industry.

The target population for this study is construction professionals, and the sampling method chosen is non-probability voluntary sampling. Potential participants expressing interest in the study were selected using a quota sampling technique, ensuring a diverse representation among the respondents. This approach was intended to capture a range of perspectives within the construction professionals.

Among the thirty-three screening survey responses received, ten candidates expressed interest in participating in the interviews. The limited response rate can be attributed to the experimental nature of technology, as ACPTS is relatively still in the research and pilot testing phase within the industry (Rehman et al., 2022). Despite the modest response, the utilization of a qualitative research method through interviews proved valuable, allowing for a more in-depth exploration, and understanding of ACPTS within the industry.

Interviews with Industry

Semi-structured interviews were conducted, guided by a set of questions covering five categories: 1) Understanding and previous experiences with ACPTS, 2) Motivations and benefits of using the ACPTS, 3) Challenges and barriers to using the ACPTS, 4) Implementation and customization of the ACPTS, and 5) Impact of the ACPTS on factors like winning new business and return on investment (ROI). The interview questions were carefully crafted to reflect a blend of insights from literature, survey responses, and invaluable feedback from the industry experts. Each interview was conducted online and took between 35-50 minutes to complete.

To ensure research reliability, all interview participants, representing diverse roles based on their survey responses (see Table 4), were asked the same categorized questions in a consistent order. Responses were then coded and analyzed using standardized methods to minimize personal bias.

Four different question categories were developed by the author to cover the companies' attitudes toward ACPTS in construction projects, which include the following:

1. For participants who have used the system and want to use it again
2. For participants who used the system but are not satisfied and do not want to use it again
3. For participants who have never used the system but have it on their long-term plan and wish to use it
4. For participants who have never used the system and are not in favor of implementing it

The interviewees consisted of the industry professional participants listed in Table 4.

TABLE 4: List of the interviewees

Participant 1	BIM manager with a trial experience with ACPTS/ Not interested in implementing this system again
Participant 2	BIM manager with a trial experience with ACPTS/ Not interested in implementing this system again
Participant 3	BIM specialist with no experience with ACPTS/ Interested to implement this system
Participant 4	BIM manager with no experience with ACPTS/ Interested in implementing this system
Participant 5	BIM manager with a couple of experiences with ACPTS/ Interested in implementing this system
Participant 6	Project manager with a couple of experiences with ACPTS/ Interested in implementing this system
Participant 7	Preconstruction manager and DT specialist with no experience with ACPTS/ Interested in implementing this system
Participant 8	Owner's rep with experience with ACPTS/ Interested in implementing this system again/ Pharmaceutical project
Participant 9	Owner's rep and project manager in Government project/ No experience with ACPTS/ Not interested in implementing this system
Participant 10	BIM manager with an experience with ACPTS/ Interested in implementing this system again

Analysis and Results

Survey analysis

The findings from the survey questionnaire reveal the distribution of respondents categorized by the size of the company. Specifically, 44.83% of respondents work for construction companies with a net worth exceeding \$500 million, 34.48% fall within the \$50 to \$500 million range, 6.90% represent companies with a net worth between \$5 to \$50 million, and 13.79% are from firms with a net worth up to \$5 million. Notably, there were no respondents from the residential sector (single-family, multi-family). In contrast, the commercial sector (comprising offices, retail, medical, and education) accounted for 64.71% of respondents, the industrial sector (encompassing automotive, tech, manufacturing, oil & gas) constituted 11.76%, and the heavy civil sector (encompassing highways, transit, power generation, and distribution) represented 23.53%.

In terms of the respondents' current roles, 24.14% were project engineers, 24.14% were BIM managers, and an additional 24.14% held executive/management positions. The remaining participants encompassed a diverse array of job titles, including assistant project managers, superintendents, estimators/schedulers, and others. Table 5 shows the responses to the survey questions. The survey responses helped in formulating interview questions across four distinct categories, each reflecting the diverse experiences and interests of experts in ACPTS.

TABLE 5: Summary of survey responses for ACPTS

Questions	Yes	No	Maybe	Definitely	Probably	Definitely	Probably	Unsure
				Yes	Yes	No	Not	
Used ACPTS before?	31%	69%	-	-	-	-	-	-
Interested in future use?	68.4%	31.5%	-	-	-	-	-	-
Had a champion for use?	69.5%	30.5%	-	-	-	-	-	-
Recommend to other GCs?	21%	68.5%	10.5%	-	-	-	-	-
Faced challenges with ACPTS?	70%	30%	-	-	-	-	-	-
Worth the investment?	-	-	-	19.3%	30.7%	-	15.4%	34.6%
Improves outcomes?	-	-	-	22.2%	44.4%	3.7%	7.5%	22.2%
Lessons learned?	24%	76%	-	-	-	-	-	-

Thematic Analysis and Data Interpretation

A total of ten interviews were conducted with the participants listed in Table 4. Once all interviews were completed, the author transcribed the interviews and employed a thematic content analysis using a systematic manual coding process. This involved categorizing responses into the four themes. This allowed the author to not only validate the initial categories but also uncover deeper insights, such as the nuanced attitudes toward the adoption of technology and the varying levels of trust and skepticism among participants.

The first theme, Financial Consideration, highlights the monetary considerations and challenges faced by stakeholders. Following this, Technical Consideration discusses the technical barriers and advantages of the ACPTS. Delving into Cultural Consideration, the author observed a range of responses from enthusiastic embrace to cautious skepticism in adopting and using ACPTS, emphasizing the influence of personal and organizational cultures in technology adoption. The theme of Personal Consideration highlights perspectives that originate from personal standpoints and experiences, which could not be accommodated within the other mentioned themes.

Table 6 highlights the drivers and barriers of ACPTS for construction projects, derived from the interviews.

TABLE 6: Drivers and Barriers of ACPTS

Drivers of ACPTS Use	Less Labor Needed – Decreased manpower needed for progress tracking	Financial
	Facilitated Payment Application – Easier process for validating and processing payments	Financial
	Automated EVM and Schedule Report – Automatically create earned value and scheduling progress reports	Financial
	Efficiency Improvement – Enhanced efficiency as a result of using automated systems	Technical
	Time-Saving Validation – Reduction in time required for validating project progress	Technical
	Data-Driven Decision Making – Emphasis on using objective data for project decisions	Technical
	Quantitative Tracking Benefits – Advantages of having measurable tracking of progress	Technical
	Document Integration Capability – Ability to incorporate various project documents	Technical
	Remote Project Monitoring – Facilitation of project oversight from distant locations	Technical
	Data-Driven Project Management – The shift towards using accurate BIM models and DT for more informed project management	Technical
	Project Success Measurement – Available static data for measuring progress success to find the shortcomings	Technical
	Effective Resource Allocation – The ACPTS impact on resource distribution aligning with project schedules	Technical
	Proactive Management Desire – Preference for a more advanced management approach	Cultural
	Early Intervention Strategy – Capability to address issues promptly before escalation	Cultural
	Trust and Verification – Use of technology to build trust and verify progress with owners	Personal
Communication Enhancement – Better communication among stakeholders	Personal	

Barriers to Using ACPTS	Schedule Control – Assists with maintaining schedule control	Personal
	Technology as a Competitive Edge – Technological capabilities help in winning contracts and retaining clients.	Personal
	Better Decision Making – Facilitated and more informed decision-making processes.	Personal
	Cost Constraints – Potential high expenses associated with implementation and usage	Financial
	Limited Perceived Value – Questionable return on investment from the GC's perspective.	Financial
	Challenges in Procurement for Government Projects – Points to difficulties in acquiring new software or technology due to bureaucratic procedures	Financial
	Baseline BIM Model Development – The creation of a detailed initial BIM model at the start of the construction project for digital twin processes is required	Financial
	Time-consuming Updates – The practice of continuously updating the BIM model to reflect actual construction progress in digital twin model – The integration of digital twins and BIM is not fully automated and requires manual effort	Financial
	Complexity of Setup – Challenges in installation and initial setup of the system and unexpected labor intensity in system setup and data input	Technical
	Integration Challenges – Difficulty in integrating new systems with existing tools	Technical
	Data Overload – Excess information generated that is not useful for progress tracking	Technical
	Data Validation Effort – Significant effort required to validate data from automated systems	Technical
	Software Flexibility Limitations – Constraints in selecting or changing software tools	Technical
	Challenges in AR Accuracy – Difficulties in achieving precise accuracy with AR, crucial in tight spaces	Technical
	Learning Curve for AI – Initial difficulty in AI adaptation due to lack of historical data	Technical
	Low-Tech Government Projects – Preference or prevalence of low-tech approaches in government-related construction projects	Cultural
	Construction Technology Fatigue – Challenges with adapting to constant changes in technology	Cultural
	Short-Term Implementation Issues – Short-term tech trials overlook long-term benefits	Cultural
Lack of Ease of Use – Lack of user-friendly interfaces and simplified operation, which requires experienced users to be comfortable with software tools.	Personal	
Trust and skepticism in AI Technology – Concerns about the reliability and acceptance of AI-generated data	Personal	
Uncertain Implementation Expectations – Challenges in understanding and meeting expectations for new tool implementation	Personal	

Results

Theme 1: Financial Consideration

Nine interviewees cited financial concerns as a major obstacle to adopting ACPTS and related technologies in construction projects. The cost was repeatedly mentioned as a barrier, stemming

from budget limitations and fear of high initial expenses with uncertain returns. This aligns with previous research highlighting cost as a primary challenge in ACPTS adoption (Moselhi et al., 2020; Omar et al., 2016). Two of the interviewees emphasized the importance of clear financial benefits for technological adoption; without them, contractors may be dismissive. Additionally, five interviewees noted that relying on owner funding often leads to a passive stance among construction professionals toward the adoption of ACPTS.

In the interviews, a recurring trend emerged: Four interviewees highlighted the owners' hesitation to allocate funds for technological advancements, favoring traditional project expenses. This reluctance is compounded by the industry's reliance on word-of-mouth recommendations, leading to slow adoption of innovative tools. One interviewee emphasized that until the benefits of emerging technologies and AI are fully realized and widely accepted within the industry, owners may remain skeptical about investing in what is perceived as costly, high-tech solutions without proven track records of delivering value. Therefore, there is a need for more comprehensive research focused on assessing the ROI in investing in and using ACPTS.

The preference for manual tracking persists despite all the interviewees acknowledging its inefficiency in cost and schedule control, exacerbating financial challenges in technology adoption. All interviewees consistently noted that reliance on traditional methods often leads to projects being over budget and behind schedule, aligning with previous research (Golparvar-Fard et al., 2009). However, there's resistance to investing in innovative technology, driven by the belief in the adequacy of cheaper, established methods over potential innovation. Nevertheless, insights from three of the interviewees challenge this skepticism, asserting that while initial costs of ACPTS may seem high, reduced labor costs, enhanced data processing efficiency, and cost-effective pricing models make it financially viable. These insights contradict prevailing views and emphasize reevaluating the perceived expense of ACPTS considering its long-term cost-saving potential.

For instance, one interviewee shared how ACPTS rectified issues in a previous project, improving progress-tracking, decision-making, and communication with the general contractor, consistent with barriers of traditional progress-tracking systems (Golparvar-Fard et al., 2015). Implementing ACPTS enabled real-time updates and dynamic intervention, ensuring the project met the owner's expectations and reducing the need for rework. A tangible example of its effectiveness was observed by the interviewee in the owner's previous project, where a laboratory was built with exposed conduits, breaching regulations. To avoid such issues in future projects, the owner invested in ACPTS and BIM, facilitating better change tracking and ensuring regulatory compliance. Findings from Omar et al. (2016) support the use of ACPTS and BIM, revealing lower rework rates in construction projects. Despite this, concerns about slim profit margins in the construction industry indicate that project owners, rather than contractors, may need to bear the technological costs. As mentioned by one of the interviewees, ACPTS primarily benefits subcontractors by showcasing productivity and work progress, which may not be as relevant to general contractors focused on overall schedule adherence. Consequently, technology is often used for marketing to owners rather than operational benefits, as highlighted by the responses of four of the interviewees.

Theme 2: Technical Consideration

Technical considerations encompass the issues, barriers, and drivers observed by interviewees regarding the use of ACPTS and DT technology, influencing attitudes toward their implementation. Resistance to ACPTS is linked to its complex setup procedures and learning curve, consistent with literature highlighting setup complexity (Ekanayake et al., 2021) and skepticism surrounding the motives behind promoting these technologies in construction projects. One interviewee experienced in DT technology noted that although a significant portion of jobsite data can be transformed into mesh models, manual intervention is still necessary, preventing DTs from being fully functional ACPTS. This manual intervention, typically managed by third-party service providers, can be cost-effective for projects requiring regular updates during construction.

The demand for user-friendly technology integrating seamlessly into existing workflows was highlighted by six of the interviewees, suggesting potential openness to adoption. However, this enthusiasm is balanced by considerations of long-term benefits and integration challenges. Five of the interviewees noted the value of features such as custom dashboards and 360-camera utilization for improving monitoring and reporting. Nevertheless, one interviewee raised concerns about customization complexity, privacy issues (Patel et al., 2022), and integration with existing construction scheduling software packages.

Two of the interviewees provided insightful perspectives regarding the impact of technologies on GC-owner relationships. In one instance, an owner used the system to pressure the general contractor for schedule delays, revealing that while these technologies enhance transparency and efficiency, they may also introduce challenges in stakeholder relationships, potentially leading to leverage or mistrust. However, six of the interviewees noted that close collaboration between the owner and GC can maximize ACPTS utilization, ensuring high-quality project completion. For example, one interviewee cited facilitated payment applications as a key ACPTS driver, noting positive feedback, garnering positive feedback from those seeking streamlined financial processes and up-to-date invoices. This finding aligns with (Turkan et al., 2013), advocating for a fully automated system to track progress and generate earned value reports.

Additionally, while the system automates earned value and progress reports, one interviewee pointed out the significant upfront preparation and manual work needed. The interviewee highlighted a gap between the perceived ease of technology use and the practical implementation challenges, which require substantial investments in resources, time, and effort to fully realize their benefits. An interviewee described 'technology fatigue,' revealing resistance to implementation due to frequent technological changes. They prefer a comprehensive system meeting all needs without frequent updates.

Furthermore, limitations in quality control were highlighted as a significant concern. Five of the interviewees expressed skepticism or resistance toward fully relying on automated systems for quality control. They noted that while ACPTS excels at tracking installed work, they lack the capability to assess installation quality. This deficiency necessitates the involvement of inspectors and project stakeholders to ensure quality and safety standards are met, casting doubt on the assumption that technology can substantially save time and labor in construction projects.

On the other hand, eight of the interviewees highlighted that early clash detection significantly reduces errors and rework in construction projects, leading to savings in both schedule and cost which aligns with the findings in (Omar et al., 2016). Eight of the interviewees with experience working with ACPTS, particularly vision-based ones, praised the system's ability to integrate documents. They valued the centralized documentation feature, which collates schedules, earned value reports, BIM models, change order justification, and 360-degree photos for future reference. Referring to one of the interviewees with experience in DT and XR technologies, keeping the BIM model updated based on progress-tracking is crucial, as it can be used with AR systems for quality assurance and control purposes. This result aligns with (Pal et al., 2023), which discussed the automation in a vision-based DT automated progress-tracking system.

The reliance on expert personnel to implement and manage these technologies and generated data is an important consideration. For example, one interviewee with experience with RFID tags to track curtain wall installation highlighted the importance of an expert in data analysis for the project. The interviewee explained that in a complex project involving prefabricated glass walls, the team devised a method to streamline installation and material delivery by tagging the glass walls with RFID tags. This innovation allowed for automatic tracking and verification of both material delivery and the installation process.

Another significant driver, mentioned by an interviewee, was the capability for remote project monitoring. This feature provides project executives, BIM managers, and project managers with access to information from multiple or distant sites, thereby facilitating a more informed decision-making process.

Theme 3: Cultural Consideration

The perceptions of subcontractor performance monitoring were mixed among the interviewees. According to an interviewee's viewpoint, ACPTS may assist in enhancing oversight, yet it might also be perceived negatively as micromanagement by others. Moreover, two of the interviewees mentioned that the sophistication level of the project owner also plays a role. So, more tech-savvy owners, like healthcare project owners, are open to technology adoption, while less tech-savvy ones, like government project owners, may view progress-tracking as the contractors' responsibility. Furthermore, educated owners recognize that ACPTS can be potential trust-building tools, enhancing transparency and accountability.

One interviewee believed that inadequate trust in project performance can motivate adoption to ensure accountability. However, reluctance from key personnel like superintendents and project engineers, often due to a lack of awareness, poses a significant barrier to implementation, as mentioned by seven of the interviewees. Supporting this, X. Chen et al. (2022) highlighted the need for education and training for successful technology implementation in the construction industry. All interview participants agreed that while there may be motivation from the technology department, widespread implementation will not happen unless frontline employees such as project managers and superintendents see it as necessary on the jobsite. This calls for education, and three of the interviewees mentioned conducting training to promote technology implementation in their projects, indicating that broader adoption is a matter of time. Rehman et al. (2022) conducted research that revealed a significant lack of awareness among industry experts

about the techniques and capabilities of ACPTS. This finding highlights a gap in knowledge within the industry regarding ACPTS technologies.

While communication enhancement is an anticipated ACPTS benefit based on the findings from (Ekanayake et al., 2021; Omar et al., 2016; Pan et al., 2021), one interviewee questioned the practical application. The interviewee expressed that some managers might view technology as a threat to their control. This is because technology allows owners and other stakeholders to monitor project progress in real-time, potentially reducing the managers' exclusive oversight.

An interviewee working on government projects highlighted resistance to innovative technologies, especially in federal projects that rely on traditional methods. The interviewee expressed frustration with rigid procurement and acquisition rules, which limit flexibility in adopting innovative approaches, particularly for software or software-as-a-service solutions. The interviewee also pointed out the extensive manual data entry and system manipulation, which signifies a lack of automation. This reliance on manual processes leads to inefficiencies, potentially affecting project schedules and timelines. This finding aligns with previous research findings that highlighted the inefficiencies of traditional progress-tracking systems (Golparvar-Fard et al., 2011, Elazouni & Abdel-Wahhab, 2009).

Theme 4: Personal Consideration

One interviewee with experience using ACPTS emphasized the importance of managing realistic expectations to balance enthusiasm and practicality, thereby reducing potential disappointment. This interviewee noted that individuals new to ACPTS might either be excited or cautious, depending on their openness to innovation. For example, effective ACPTS deployment requires a fully coordinated BIM model; lacking this, such as when a GC cannot provide the necessary prerequisites, can lead to underwhelming results from technological implementation. From the interviewee's perspective, adoption based on solid evidence of effectiveness is essential for some individuals before they are willing to commit to new tools. The benefits of software evolution, which include learning from early adopters' feedback and system improvements, may make later adoption more appealing based on three of the interviewees who were interested in implementing this technology but have not observed any real benefits.

According to six interviewees with expertise in construction technology, the suggestion of a pilot program could signal an openness to experimentation, appealing to those who favor a measured approach to change and may influence attitudes positively. Knowledge sharing across companies can also encourage a collaborative spirit, fostering receptiveness to new technologies (X. Chen et al., 2022).

Viewing technology as a competitive advantage can foster positive attitudes, especially when it is regarded as a market differentiator (X. Chen et al., 2022). While only three of the interviewees believed that implementing ACPTS in their projects could give them a competitive advantage to impress owners and win bids, others feel that the significance of technology in construction has not yet reached the point of being a critical factor in an owner's selection of a general contractor. Lastly, although nine of the interviewees suggested a tendency toward implementing technology

to save on cost and schedule, there is a belief that neither the industry nor construction project staff are currently ready for full ACPTS implementation, though it may happen in the future.

In summary, the thematic content analysis uncovered a complex interplay of factors impacting the adoption of ACPTS in construction. From financial, technical, cultural, and personal considerations, these themes collectively paint a comprehensive picture of the current landscape and attitudes towards technological advancement, particularly ACPTS, in the industry. Understanding these multifaceted influences is crucial for developing strategies that facilitate more effective adoption of innovative ACPTS technologies in construction projects.

Conclusion

This study aimed to review ACPTS use within the industry, using an in-depth exploration of industry perspectives in terms of the drivers and barriers to using ACPTS. Qualitative data was collected from industry experts to identify these barriers and drivers of ACPTS in the construction sector. The analysis of interview data revealed four distinct consideration themes in relation to the challenges and benefits of ACPTS implementation in the construction industry, which include financial, technical, cultural, and personal considerations. Each theme encompasses several factors influencing the adoption and efficacy of ACPTS.

In reviewing the process of this study, it is important to acknowledge certain limitations. The primary limitation was the low response rate to the surveys and the limited number of interview participants, which means the findings should not be generalized to a larger population. This limitation can largely be attributed to the limited implementation of this technology and its current status as an emerging technology. As more information becomes available and more firms show interest in investing in and implementing ACPTS, this study could be enhanced by conducting case studies on both successful and unsuccessful uses of ACPTS. Furthermore, while a range of perspectives was sought and achieved, there is a possibility of participant self-selection bias due to the voluntary nature of the survey and interviews, as participants with a prior interest in or experience with ACPTS might be more inclined to participate in this research. This could potentially shift the findings toward more engaged or knowledgeable respondents. Hence, Future studies could mitigate this bias incentivizing participation from those less familiar with ACPTS, to ensure a more comprehensive view of its adoption and implementation challenges.

The analysis of information from industry experts leads to the conclusion that many companies recognize deficiencies in current progress-tracking methods. There is enthusiasm for adopting newer, more accurate technologies to improve these processes. However, this transition is not yet a priority for many, and time is needed to demonstrate the effectiveness of ACPTS technologies. This suggests a wait-and-see approach is currently prevailing in the industry.

This research equips the construction industry with the knowledge needed to make informed decisions about ACPTS implementation. By understanding the advantages and challenges of different ACPTS, construction stakeholders can identify the most appropriate technologies for their projects. Additionally, insights into industry experts' perspectives on the implementation benefits and barriers guide the effective integration of ACPTS. The primary beneficiaries are

construction industry practitioners, whose awareness and willingness to experiment with new technologies are key to ACPTS's broader adoption.

In order to foster broader adoption, future research could delve into comparative case studies between traditional progress-tracking methods and ACPTS to evaluate differences in ROI, productivity, and schedule control. These studies would provide empirical evidence to better understand the advantages and limitations of ACPTS. Additionally, exploring cost-effective strategies for acquiring and implementing ACPTS is crucial, especially as the industry tends to expect immediate results, despite the need for time to observe its benefits. Another key research area is developing metrics to assess ACPTS effectiveness, as a lack of evaluated benefits has hindered adoption.

Furthermore, research is needed to explore how these findings could benefit education in construction technology. Planned future work focused on developing a workflow and roadmap for ACPTS implementation could offer valuable insights for higher education. This roadmap could guide course content and training programs by providing a step-by-step approach to ACPTS integration, better preparing construction teams for the practical challenges of implementing this technology in real-world projects.

References

- Abreu, N., Pinto, A., Matos, A., & Pires, M. (2023, 20-23 June 2023). *Construction progress monitoring – A virtual reality based platform*. Paper presented at the 2023 18th Iberian Conference on Information Systems and Technologies (CISTI).
- Alizadehsalehi, S., & Yitmen, I. (2019a). A concept for automated construction progress monitoring: technologies adoption for benchmarking project performance control. *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, 44, 4993-5008.
- Alizadehsalehi, S., & Yitmen, I. (2019b). A Concept for Automated Construction Progress Monitoring: Technologies Adoption for Benchmarking Project Performance Control. *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, 44(5), 4993-5008. doi:10.1007/s13369-018-3669-1
- Amirthavarshan, K., Gallage, S., Costa, M., & Eranga, B. (2023). Potential use of digital twin for construction progress monitoring.
- Asadi, K., Ramshankar, H., Noghabaei, M., & Han, K. (2019). Real-time image localization and registration with BIM using perspective alignment for indoor monitoring of construction. *Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering*, 33(5), 04019031.
- Boje, C., Guerriero, A., Kubicki, S., & Rezgui, Y. (2020). Towards a semantic Construction Digital Twin: Directions for future research. *Automation in Construction*, 114, 103179. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103179>
- Chen, J., Kira, Z., & Cho, Y. K. (2019). Deep Learning Approach to Point Cloud Scene Understanding for Automated Scan to 3D Reconstruction. *Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering*, 33(4), 04019027. doi:doi:10.1061/(ASCE)CP.1943-5487.0000842
- Chen, X., Chang-Richards, A. Y., Pelosi, A., Jia, Y., Shen, X., Siddiqui, M. K., & Yang, N. (2022). Implementation of technologies in the construction industry: a systematic review.

- Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 29(8), 3181-3209.
doi:10.1108/ECAM-02-2021-0172
- Côté, S., Trudel, P., Desbiens, M., Giguère, M., & Snyder, R. (2013). Live mobile panoramic high accuracy augmented reality for engineering and construction. *Proceedings of the Construction Applications of Virtual Reality (CONVR), London, England*, 1-10.
- Davila Delgado, J. M., Oyedele, L., Ajayi, A., Akanbi, L., Akinade, O., Bilal, M., & Owolabi, H. (2019). Robotics and automated systems in construction: Understanding industry-specific challenges for adoption. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 26, 100868.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2019.100868>
- Deng, H., Hong, H., Luo, D., Deng, Y., & Su, C. (2020). Automatic Indoor Construction Process Monitoring for Tiles Based on BIM and Computer Vision. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 146(1), 04019095. doi:doi:10.1061/(ASCE)CO.1943-7862.0001744
- Ekanayake, B., Wong, J. K.-W., Fini, A. A. F., & Smith, P. (2021). Computer vision-based interior construction progress monitoring: A literature review and future research directions. *Automation in Construction*, 127, 103705. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2021.103705>
- Golparvar-Fard, M., Bohn, J., Teizer, J., Savarese, S., & Peña-Mora, F. (2011). Evaluation of image-based modeling and laser scanning accuracy for emerging automated performance monitoring techniques. *Automation in Construction*, 20(8), 1143-1155.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2011.04.016>
- Golparvar-Fard, M., Pena-Mora, F., & Savarese, S. (2015). Automated progress monitoring using unordered daily construction photographs and IFC-based building information models. *Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering*, 29(1), 04014025.
- Golparvar-Fard, M., Peña-Mora, F., & Savarese, S. (2009). D4AR—a 4-dimensional augmented reality model for automating construction progress monitoring data collection, processing and communication. *Journal of information technology in construction*, 14(13), 129-153.
- Halder, S., Afsari, K., Serdakowski, J., DeVito, S., Ensafi, M., & Thabet, W. (2022). Real-Time and Remote Construction Progress Monitoring with a Quadraped Robot Using Augmented Reality. *Buildings*, 12(11), 2027.
- Hegazy, T. (2013). *Computer-based construction project management: Pearson new international edition*: Pearson Higher Ed.
- Kopsida. (2015). *A Review of Automated Construction Progress Monitoring and Inspection Methods*.
- Kopsida, M., Brilakis, I., & Vela, P. A. (2015). *A review of automated construction progress monitoring and inspection methods*. Paper presented at the Proc. of the 32nd CIB W78 Conference 2015.
- Li, T., Liu, J., Zhang, W., Ni, Y., Wang, W., & Li, Z. (2021). *Uav-human: A large benchmark for human behavior understanding with unmanned aerial vehicles*. Paper presented at the Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition.
- Ma, Z. (2019). *A Real-Time 4D Augmented Reality System for Modular Construction Progress Monitoring*. Paper presented at the Proceedings of the 36th International Symposium on Automation and Robotics in Construction (ISARC).
- Morris, B. (2003). The components of the Wired Spanning Forest are recurrent. *Probability Theory and Related Fields*, 125(2), 259-265. doi:10.1007/s00440-002-0236-0
- Moselhi, O., Bardareh, H., & Zhu, Z. (2020). Automated data acquisition in construction with remote sensing technologies. *Applied Sciences*, 10(8), 2846.

- Najibifar, Y., Hemmatian, A., & Shakouri, S. (2025). *Smart Construction Site Management: IOT, Sensors, and Real-Time Monitoring*: Heritage Branch, Library and Archives Canada.
- Omar, T., & Nehdi, M. L. (2016). Data acquisition technologies for construction progress tracking. *Automation in Construction*, 70, 143-155.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2016.06.016>
- Omar, T., & Nehdi, M. L. (2018). *Automated data collection for progress tracking purposes: a review of related techniques*. Paper presented at the Facing the Challenges in Structural Engineering: Proceedings of the 1st GeoMEast International Congress and Exhibition, Egypt 2017 on Sustainable Civil Infrastructures 1.
- Pal, A., Lin, J. J., Hsieh, S.-H., & Golparvar-Fard, M. (2023). Automated vision-based construction progress monitoring in built environment through digital twin. *Developments in the Built Environment*, 100247.
- Pal, A., Lin, J. J., Hsieh, S.-H., & Golparvar-Fard, M. (2024). Activity-level construction progress monitoring through semantic segmentation of 3D-informed orthographic images. *Automation in Construction*, 157, 105157. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2023.105157>
- Pan, Y., & Zhang, L. (2021). Roles of artificial intelligence in construction engineering and management: A critical review and future trends. *Automation in Construction*, 122, 103517.
- Park, J., & Cho, Y. K. (2022). Point cloud information modeling: Deep learning-based automated information modeling framework for point cloud data. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 148(2), 04021191.
- Patel, T., Guo, B. H., Zou, Y. J. E., Construction, & Management, A. (2022). A scientometric review of construction progress monitoring studies. 29(9), 3237-3266.
- Pecoraro, J., Harper, C., & Wang, C. (2017). Unmanned aircraft systems in construction and agriculture: uses, benefits, challenges, and why companies choose to invest. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Project Management*, 7(2), 34-44.
- Rebolj, D., Babič, N. Č., Magdič, A., Podbreznik, P., & Pšunder, M. (2008). Automated construction activity monitoring system. *Advanced engineering informatics*, 22(4), 493-503.
- redacted. (2025a). *Digital Twins in Construction: From Design to Facility Management*: Heritage Branch, Library and Archives Canada.
- redacted. (2025b). Tracking BIM Coordination Progress with Power BI: A Case Study in Visual Clash Management
- Rehman, M. S. U., & Shafiq, M. T. (2022). Automated Construction Progress Monitoring—Industry Perspective.
- Reja, V. K., Varghese, K., & Ha, Q. P. (2022). Computer vision-based construction progress monitoring. *Automation in Construction*, 138, 104245.
- Sacks, R., Brilakis, I., Pikas, E., Xie, H. S., & Girolami, M. (2020). Construction with digital twin information systems. *Data-Centric Engineering*, 1, e14.
- Sami Ur Rehman, M. (2022). Automated Computer Vision-Based Construction Progress Monitoring: A Systematic Review. *Buildings*, 12(7), 1037.
- Sami Ur Rehman, M., Shafiq, M. T., & Ullah, F. (2022a). Automated Computer Vision-Based Construction Progress Monitoring: A Systematic Review. *Buildings*, 12(7), 1037.
- Sami Ur Rehman, M., Thaheem, M. J., Nasir, A. R., & Khan, K. I. A. (2022b). Project schedule risk management through building information modelling. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 22(8), 1489-1499.

- Simchenko, N., Tsohla, S., & Chyvatkin, P. (2019). IoT & digital twins concept integration effects on supply chain strategy: Challenges and effect. *International Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 8(6), 803-808.
- Singh, M., Fuenmayor, E., Hinchy, E. P., Qiao, Y., Murray, N., & Devine, D. (2021). Digital Twin: Origin to Future. *Applied System Innovation*, 4(2), 36.
- Turkan, Y., Bosché, F., Haas, C. T., & Haas, R. (2013). Toward Automated Earned Value Tracking Using 3D Imaging Tools. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 139(4), 423-433. doi:doi:10.1061/(ASCE)CO.1943-7862.0000629
- Wang, Z., Zhang, Q., Yang, B., Wu, T., Lei, K., Zhang, B., & Fang, T. (2021). Vision-Based Framework for Automatic Progress Monitoring of Precast Walls by Using Surveillance Videos during the Construction Phase. *Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering*, 35(1), 04020056. doi:doi:10.1061/(ASCE)CP.1943-5487.0000933
- Zhang, C., & Arditi, D. (2013). Automated progress control using laser scanning technology. *Automation in Construction*, 36, 108-116.